

Out-of-oven Manufacturing for Natural Fibre Composites with Integrated Deformation Sensing

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Sustainable materials

Unsustainable manufacturing

Energy inefficiency in convection heating

Energy efficient Out-of-Oven
manufacturing

Comparison of Energy Consumption

Mgbemena C O, Li D, Lin M F, et al. Accelerated microwave curing of fibre-reinforced thermoset polymer composites for structural applications: A review of scientific challenges[J]. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2018, 115: 88-103.

Resistance of PCL/GNP nanocomposites

	Thermal expansion coefficient ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)
PLA	40-60
PBAT	70-80
PCL	130-160

Dynamic mechanical analysis

Three-point bending

Joule heating curing does not affect laminate properties.

DSC analysis through the thickness

Joule heating curing does not affect laminate properties.

Damage sensing based on piezoresistive methods

Deformation and damage sensing

Self-regulated heating for energy efficient manufacturing

- Resistance signal corresponding to the strain.
- Monitor sample deformation.

Clear correlation established between damage and sensing signals

Good adhesion to the laminate surface after the failure in damage sensing

- 90 % energy savings.
- Self-regulating heating for safety.
- No effects on laminate properties.
- New functions introduced (e.g. sensing).
- Good adhesion to the laminates.

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